

Proving that $(x + 1)^1 \neq x + 1$

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Abstract

I will be proving that $(x + 1)^1 \neq x + 1$, then I will prove that the integral of $\frac{1}{x}$ is not $\ln x$ in fact is missing an entire pole, and this pole reverses the information lost when differentiating a constant, making the $+C$ we add after integrating unnecessary, and in the process will be revealing infinitely small terms that was hidden from our sights, that will allow me to show the proper expansion of $(x + 1)^1$, then I will be showing the regularization of diverging integrals for $\int_0^1 x^n dx$ when $n < -1$ and a relation that converts $\int_0^\infty f(x) dx$ into $\sum_{n=1}^\infty f(n)$ using the mclaurin series and the zeta function, which could also be used to get high accuracy approximations like $\sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{1}{n(e^n-1)} \approx \frac{\pi^2}{6} - \frac{\ln 2\pi}{2} - \frac{1}{24}$, I will also show that $\int_{-\infty}^\infty \frac{1}{\Gamma(x)} dx = e$.

1 Introduction

Before starting I want to explain some of the terms and symbols I have used in this paper.

I have used the letter h which represents an infinitely small positive value, for simplicity I also called it a zero. so h or 0 is a first degree zero, h^2 or 0^2 is a second degree zero and so on, on the other hand $\frac{1}{h}$ or $\frac{1}{0}$ is a first degree pole, $\frac{1}{h^2}$ or $\frac{1}{0^2}$ is a second degree pole and so on.

I have used the term *normal value* which represent the finite numbers like $1, 2$ or $10^{10^{10}}$ or $\frac{1}{10^{10^{10}}}$, I have used the term *small value* which represents the infinitely small values like h or 0 or h^2 or 0^2 , I also have used the term *large value* which represents the infinitely big values like $\frac{1}{h}$ or $\frac{1}{0}$ or $\frac{1}{h^2}$ or $\frac{1}{0^2}$

If I used the term area in this paper then I am talking about the area under the curve. Also I am supposed to use x^h to describe a constant but sometimes doing so will make it messy, so I did not always do that. The zeta symbol I used in this paper is for the Riemann zeta function.

Lastly I would put r in front of a diverging sum or diverging integral to take the regularization, for example $r \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n = -\frac{1}{12}$, $r(\infty!) = (2\pi)^{0.5}$ [1],

and I would put r/c to take the regularization when the sum or integral diverges and to take the actual value when the sum or integral converges, for example $r/c \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \zeta(s)$

2 Proving that $(x + 1)^1 \neq x + 1$

2.1 Proof 1

Since the sum of all natural numbers gives us $A - \frac{1}{12}$ where A is a divergent part and $-\frac{1}{12}$ is a regularized part $\zeta(-1)$, see [2], meanwhile the sum $1+1+1+1+\dots$ we will get $B - \frac{1}{2}$ where B is another divergent part but is obviously smaller than A and $-\frac{1}{2}$ is a regularized part $\zeta(0)$. So:

$$1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + \dots = A - \frac{1}{12} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n \quad (2.1)$$

Now I want to start the sum from the 2 instead of the 1, so I will shift the sum 1 unit to the left...

$$2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + \dots = A - \frac{13}{12} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n + 1)^1 \quad (2.2)$$

$$A - \frac{13}{12} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n + 1)^1 \quad (2.3)$$

Now let's suppose that $(n + 1)^1 = n + 1$

$$A - \frac{13}{12} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 1 \quad (2.4)$$

$$A - \frac{13}{12} = \left(A - \frac{1}{12}\right) + \left(B - \frac{1}{2}\right) \quad (2.5)$$

$$A - \frac{13}{12} \neq A + B - \frac{7}{12} \quad (2.6)$$

Contradiction... In section 3 I will show how $(n+1)^1$ is different from $n+1$ and I will be expanding $(n+1)^1$ properly which will give us the missing piece $(-\frac{1}{2})$ hence giving us the correct regularised value $-\frac{13}{12}$ instead of $-\frac{7}{12}$.

2.2 Proof 2

Again I will assume the expansion of $(x+1)^1$ is $x+1$, now I will integrate both sides but without expanding the left side (using integration by substitution):

$$\int (x+1)^1 dx = \int x dx + \int 1 dx \quad (2.7)$$

$$\frac{(x+1)^2}{2} \neq \frac{x^2}{2} + x \quad (2.8)$$

$$\frac{x^2}{2} + x + \frac{1}{2} \neq \frac{x^2}{2} + x \quad (2.9)$$

In Section 3 I will show how to properly expand $(x+1)^1$ and this proper expansion when integrated will produce a $\frac{1}{2}$ for the right side, making both sides equal. In next section I will also show you why I did not add $+C$.

3 $\int \frac{1}{x} dx \neq \ln x$

I always had doubts about $\int \frac{1}{x} dx = \ln x$, since if we integrate x^n for any value of n the integral will simply be $\frac{x^{n+1}}{n+1}$, $n=-1$ being the only exception giving $\ln x$ which feels so odd.

To end this internal debate I up came with a simple method for finding the integral of $\frac{1}{x}$, since integrating $\frac{1}{x}$ gives $\frac{x^0}{0}$ which is a limit, I will approach $\frac{1}{x}$ from left and right and get closer and closer to $n=-1$, integrating then summing both results and dividing by 2 to get the average value:

$$\frac{\int x^{-0.9} dx + \int x^{-1.1} dx}{2} \quad (3.1)$$

Plotting the results will give me a function that looks pretty similar to $\ln x$ but a bit off, and as I approach the -1 even more using -0.99 and -1.01 then

using -0.999 and -1.001 and so on, the plots start getting closer and closer visually to $\ln x$ until I reach a point where I can not differentiate between them.

Fast forward I was trying to find the exact value of $\zeta(1)$ which is a pole, so I remembered the method that I used to find the integral of $\frac{1}{x}$, approaching $\zeta(1)$ from left and right and getting closer and closer to the 1 (here we do not need to integrate), performing this technique approaches γ where γ is Euler–Mascheroni constant. But I know $\zeta(1)$ has to be a pole, then it hit me... this technique that I use cancels out an entire pole, this means the integral of $\frac{1}{x}$ is $\ln x + \frac{1}{0}$ (please note that when I approach a pole I use 0.9, 0.99, 0.999 which allows me to compare the degree of different poles, for $\zeta(1)$ and the integral of $\frac{1}{x}$ they both have a first degree pole ($\frac{1}{0}$) but for example $\frac{1}{x^2}$ at $x=0$ has a second degree pole ($\frac{1}{0^2}$))

Since:

$$e^n = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(1)^k}{k!} \quad (3.2)$$

Then:

$$e^{n \ln x} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(n \ln x)^k}{k!} \quad (3.3)$$

So:

$$x^n = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(n \ln x)^k}{k!} \quad (3.4)$$

Subbing in $n=0$

$$x^0 = 1 + \frac{(0 \ln x)^1}{1!} + \frac{(0 \ln x)^2}{2!} + \frac{(0 \ln x)^3}{3!} + \frac{(0 \ln x)^4}{4!} \dots \quad (3.5)$$

Dividing by 0:

$$\frac{x^0}{0} = \frac{1}{0} + \ln x + \frac{(0)(\ln x)^2}{2!} + \frac{(0)^2(\ln x)^3}{3!} + \frac{(0)^3(\ln x)^4}{4!} \dots \quad (3.6)$$

As we can see the first 2 terms are $\frac{1}{0} + \ln x$ as I predicted (the other terms did not show up because they are zeroes), so it is pretty clear to me that the integral of $\frac{1}{x}$ is $\frac{x^0}{0}$.

Now I will be showing one of the common proofs that is used to prove that $\int \frac{1}{x} dx = \ln x$ and where the mistake happens. Assume $x = e^y$ which gives $\ln x = y$

So:

$$\frac{dx}{dy} = x \quad (3.7)$$

$$\frac{dx}{x} = dy \quad (3.8)$$

Now:

$$\int 1 \frac{dx}{x} = \int 1 dy = y = \ln x \quad (3.9)$$

As we can see this proves that $\int \frac{1}{x} dx = \ln x$ but now I will use $x^0 = 1$

Now:

$$\int 1 \frac{dx}{x} = \int x^0 \frac{dx}{x} = \int x^0 dy \quad (3.10)$$

Since $x = e^y$ then $x^0 = (e^y)^0 = e^{0y}$

$$\int e^{0y} dy = \frac{e^{0y}}{0} = \frac{x^0}{0} \quad (3.11)$$

As we can see I got two different results depending if I used 1 or x^0 , and since $x^0 = 1$ then this means $\ln x = \frac{x^0}{0}$ which also means $\ln x = \frac{1}{0}$, in what world does dividing a constant by another constant gives a function? It is simply impossible, this means $x^0 \neq 1$, and it is trivial that any $f(x)$ is multiplied by x^0 and by 1, 1 will have no effect but x^0 will have an effect when integrating by substitution just like what happened in (3.10) and (3.11), which means that (3.9) is missing an important step (multiplying by x^0) so the integral of $\int \frac{1}{x} dx = \frac{x^0}{0}$

Now I will show how using $\frac{x^0}{0}$ instead of the $\ln x$ reverses the information lost when differentiating a constant, In order to show that I will use e^x due to its immunity to change when differentiating and integrating, since:

$$e^x = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(x)^n}{n!} \quad (3.12)$$

So:

$$e^x = \frac{x^0}{0!} + \frac{x^1}{1!} + \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^3}{3!} + \frac{x^4}{4!} \dots \quad (3.13)$$

If I differentiate both sides they will stay the same but if I integrate both sides I will get:

$$e^x = \frac{x^1}{1!} + \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^3}{3!} + \frac{x^4}{4!} + \frac{x^5}{5!} \dots \quad (3.14)$$

$$e^x \neq e^x - \frac{x^0}{0!} \quad (3.15)$$

I know I will be told that I have to add +C to fix this issue, but I will fix it without the need for +C. First thing we have to notice in the mclaurin series at (3.13) is how the previous term is the derivate of the next term, so I will start from the left and diffrentiate my way to the right (this will produce the terms of the mclaurin series), now:

$$\frac{x^4}{4!} \rightarrow \frac{4x^3}{4!} \rightarrow \frac{4 * 3x^2}{4!} \rightarrow \frac{4 * 3 * 2x^1}{4!} \rightarrow \frac{4 * 3 * 2 * 1x^0}{4!} \rightarrow \frac{4 * 3 * 2 * 1 * 0x^{-1}}{4!} \rightarrow \quad (3.16)$$

$$\frac{4 * 3 * 2 * 1 * 0 * -1x^{-2}}{4!} \rightarrow \frac{4 * 3 * 2 * 1 * 0 * -1 * -2x^{-3}}{4!} \quad (3.17)$$

simplifying gives

$$e^x = \dots + (0)(-1)(-2)x^{-3} + (0)(-1)x^{-2} + (0)x^{-1} + \frac{x^0}{0!} + \frac{x^1}{1!} + \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^3}{3!} + \frac{x^4}{4!} \dots \quad (3.18)$$

This is where the magic happens, it is true that the x^{-1} term of the mclaurin series is multiplied by a 0 but integrating x^{-1} gives $\frac{x^0}{0}$ so the 0 will get multiplied by a pole ($\frac{1}{0}$) cancelling each other and reversing the information lost when diffrentiating.

But since differentiating different constants involves multiplying by a zero, causing loss of information. From now on I will avoid diffrentiating x^0 instead I will diffrentiate x^h , where h is an infinitely small positive value, so from now on, I will avoid multiplying and dividing by zeroes. But this means when I diffrentiate and integrate x^h I will get: $x^{2+h}, x^{1+h}, x^h, x^{-1+h}, x^{-2+h}$ etc, so diffrentiating x^h gives hx^{-1+h} and integrating x^{-1+h} gives $\frac{x^h}{h}$

Now I will simplify (3.18) further:

$$e^x = \dots + (h)(-1)(-2)x^{-3+h} + (h)(-1)x^{-2+h} + (h)x^{-1+h} + \frac{x^h}{0!} + \frac{x^{1+h}}{1!} + \frac{x^{2+h}}{2!} + \frac{x^{3+h}}{3!} + \frac{x^{4+h}}{4!} \dots \quad (3.19)$$

since $\frac{1}{(-1+h)!} = h$, $\frac{1}{(-2+h)!} = -h$, $\frac{1}{(-3+h)!} = 2h$, $\frac{1}{(-4+h)!} = -6h$

these values are not perfect representation (they are missing h^2 , h^3 , h^4 and so on) but they are good enough for now, then:

$$e^x = \dots + \frac{x^{-3+h}}{(-3+h)!} + \frac{x^{-2+h}}{(-2+h)!} + \frac{x^{-1+h}}{(-1+h)!} + \frac{x^h}{0!} + \frac{x^{1+h}}{(1)!} + \frac{x^{2+h}}{(2)!} + \frac{x^{3+h}}{(3)!} + \frac{x^{4+h}}{(4)!} \dots \quad (3.20)$$

Now I will continue the pattern to the right side:

$$e^x = \dots + \frac{x^{-3+h}}{(-3+h)!} + \frac{x^{-2+h}}{(-2+h)!} + \frac{x^{-1+h}}{(-1+h)!} + \frac{x^h}{h!} + \frac{x^{1+h}}{(1+h)!} + \frac{x^{2+h}}{(2+h)!} + \frac{x^{3+h}}{(3+h)!} + \frac{x^{4+h}}{(4+h)!} \dots \quad (3.21)$$

As we can see adding all these h's is visually ridiculous, so for simplicity we can imagine the h's being there but I will not add them to everything on the taylor series and binomial expansion.

$$e^x = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(x)^{n+h}}{(n+h)!} \quad (3.22)$$

Basically the mclaurin series of all functions extends to the negative side and usually consists of zeroes that preserve the information about the Cx^0 (constant of integral), taylor series defintion becomes:

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{f^{n+h}(a)}{(n+h)!} (x-a)^{n+h} \quad (3.23)$$

Another example is

$$2^x = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(\ln 2)^{n+h} (x)^{n+h}}{(n+h)!} \quad (3.24)$$

$$\int 2^x dx = \int \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(\ln 2)^{n+h} (x)^{n+h}}{(n+h)!} \right) dx \quad (3.25)$$

$$\frac{2^x}{\ln 2} = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(\ln 2)^{n+h} (x)^{n+h+1}}{(n+h+1)!} \quad (3.26)$$

As we can see, when I integrated the left side the intersection with y axis was $\frac{1}{\ln 2}$ which is exactly equal to the right side, if I used the traditional definition of the Taylor series without extending it to the negative side I would have an intersection with y axis = 0 because the Maclaurin series will have no x^{-1} term that will turn into x^0 when integrating.

Since differentiating Cx^h gives $C hx^{-1+h}$ instead of just a 0, then this means that each constant will have its own unique derivative, which I can integrate to summon the constant back, this makes the +C that we add after integrating a function useless, since no information is lost about the constant anymore. But this also means that any function has a predetermined constant of integral embedded in the Maclaurin series of the function (every function will have 1 perfect integral only), for example e^x will always summon a 1 and $(x+1)^1$ will summon a $\frac{1}{2}$. (please note that in here when I am talking about the constant I am talking about the coefficient of x^h , since I showed before we can not use x^0 it will cause multiplying by a zero which deletes information)

Now I will show how $(x+1)^1$ is different from $x+1$, We know from binomial expansion for $(ax+b)^n$

$$\sum_{q=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{n! a^q b^{n-q}}{q!(n-q)!} x^q \quad (3.27)$$

For $(x+1)^1$ a=1, b=1, n=1 which becomes:

$$\sum_{q=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1!}{q!(1-q)!} x^q \quad (3.28)$$

So:

$$\dots + \frac{x^{-3+h}}{(-3)!(4!)} + \frac{x^{-2+h}}{(-2)!(3!)} + \frac{x^{-1+h}}{(-1)!(2!)} + \frac{x^h}{(0)!(1!)} + \frac{x^{1+h}}{1!(0)!} + \frac{x^{2+h}}{2!(-1)!} + \frac{x^{3+h}}{3!(-2)!} \dots \quad (3.29)$$

Now this step is very tricky, but first it is important to understand when working with functions the value of the first degree zero (h) is the derivative of the function at that point, for example if I am working with $\frac{1}{r!}$ and I want

to find the value of $(-1)!$ then I should find the derivative at that point, so deriving $\frac{1}{x!}$ and subbing in (-1) gives 1 this means the value of $(-1)!$ is a first degree zero with coefficient of 1, doing the same with $\frac{1}{(1-r)!}$ will give first degree zero with coefficient of -1, even though both are represented by $(-1)!$ but they have different directions, when working with zeroes and poles we have to treat everything in terms of a function, Now:

$$\dots + \frac{hx^{-3+h}}{12} - \frac{hx^{-2+h}}{6} + \frac{hx^{-1+h}}{2} + x^h + x^{1+h} - \frac{hx^{2+h}}{2} + \frac{hx^{3+h}}{6} \dots \quad (3.30)$$

As we can see this is what the expansion of $(x+1)^1$ actually looks like it has more terms than $x+1$, now let us integrate it:

$$\int (x+1)^1 dx = \int \left(\dots + \frac{hx^{-3}}{12} - \frac{hx^{-2}}{6} + \frac{hx^{-1+h}}{2} + x^h + x^1 - \frac{hx^2}{2} + \frac{hx^3}{6} \dots \right) dx \quad (3.31)$$

$$\frac{(x+1)^2}{2} = \left(\dots - \frac{hx^{-2}}{24} + \frac{hx^{-1+h}}{6} + \frac{x^h}{2} + x^1 + \frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{hx^3}{6} + \frac{hx^4}{24} \dots \right) \quad (3.32)$$

As we can see expanding $(x+1)^1$ properly and integrating it gave me the extra term $\frac{x^h}{2}$ which is basically the $\frac{1}{2}$ I mentioned in proof 2.2, it is also important to note that the right side expansion at (3.32) is the proper expansion of $\frac{(x+1)^2}{2}$ so if we use (3.27) to expand $\frac{(x+1)^2}{2}$ it will exactly match (3.32).

So now that I have shown how to properly expand binomial expansions and I extended Taylor series to its negative side, now I will show how to expand $(x+1)^1$ even more properly, because the expansion at (3.30) is only 1 row but actual expansion has infinite rows, to show this we first investigate:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{e^x - 1}{x} = 1 \quad (3.33)$$

this means that:

$$e^h = 1 + h + \frac{h^2}{2} + \frac{h^3}{6} + \frac{h^4}{24} \dots \quad (3.34)$$

It is true that this is based on the Taylor series and I expanded the Taylor series to the negative side but doing so will give me poles, and it gets really complicated, for now I will stick to the positive side of the Taylor series only:

$$\frac{e^h - 1}{h} = \frac{1 + h + \frac{h^2}{2} + \frac{h^3}{6} + \frac{h^4}{24} \dots - 1}{h} \quad (3.35)$$

$$\frac{e^h - 1}{h} = 1 + \frac{h^1}{2} + \frac{h^2}{6} + \frac{h^3}{24} \dots \quad (3.36)$$

So the idea is that any point in a function has an output that consists of the main constant (h^0) and different degrees of zeroes etc (h, h^2, h^3) and is based on the Taylor series of that function at that point, so:

$$(x+1)^1 = \left(\dots + \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{h}{6} \\ -\frac{5h^2}{36} \\ +\dots \end{bmatrix} x^{-2} + \begin{bmatrix} +\frac{h}{2} \\ +\frac{3h^2}{4} \\ +\dots \end{bmatrix} x^{-1+h} + \begin{bmatrix} +1 \\ +h \\ +\dots \end{bmatrix} x^h + \begin{bmatrix} +1 \\ -h \\ +\dots \end{bmatrix} x^1 + \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{h}{2} \\ +\frac{3h^2}{4} \\ +\dots \end{bmatrix} x^2 + \dots \right) \quad (3.37)$$

here I showed row 0 and row 1, row 0 is the same as I showed in (3.26), obviously there is row 2,3, ... all the way to ∞ , I also suspect there could be row -1,-2,-3... but I am not really sure about that (I could not make it work).

Now I will show how to multiply two Taylor series by each other, it is not that trivial anymore, I will multiply e^x by itself:

$$e^x = \dots + \frac{x^{-2+h}}{(-2+h)!} + \frac{x^{-1+h}}{(-1+h)!} + \frac{x^h}{(0+h)!} + \frac{x^{1+h}}{(1+h)!} + \frac{x^{2+h}}{(2+h)!} + \dots \quad (3.38)$$

if I multiply this series by itself the h's will stack and the new resulting Taylor series will have:

$$\dots + x^{-2+2h} + x^{-1+2h} + x^{0+2h} + x^{1+2h} + x^{2+2h} + \dots \quad (3.39)$$

which will make the zeroes bigger than what they actually are, so we will have to divide the value of the h's we get, if it is first degree zero we have to divide by 2, if second degree by 4, and if third degree then by 8 and so on... OR we can half the zero when inputting into the Taylor series before multiplying which will create the same effect like this:

$$e^x = \dots + \frac{x^{-2+\frac{h}{2}}}{(-2+\frac{h}{2})!} + \frac{x^{-1+\frac{h}{2}}}{(-1+\frac{h}{2})!} + \frac{x^{\frac{h}{2}}}{(0+\frac{h}{2})!} + \frac{x^{1+\frac{h}{2}}}{(1+\frac{h}{2})!} + \frac{x^{2+\frac{h}{2}}}{(2+\frac{h}{2})!} + \dots \quad (3.40)$$

Now I will fix proof 2.1

$$A - \frac{13}{12} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n+1)^1 \quad (3.41)$$

Now use proper expansion of $(n+1)^1$

$$A - \frac{13}{12} = \dots + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{h}{2n} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1+h+\dots)n^0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1-h+\dots)n + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{-hn^2}{2} + \dots \quad (3.42)$$

I will skip the diverging part (too complicated). Since I want the value of h^0 then all the h^1 will be useless except the one for the harmonic series since it will get multiplied by a pole ($\zeta(1)$), now the regularized part becomes:

$$-\frac{13}{12} = \dots + \left(\frac{h}{2}\right)\zeta(1) + (1)\zeta(0) + (1)\zeta(-1) - \left(\frac{h}{2}\right)\zeta(-2) + \dots \quad (3.43)$$

$$-\frac{13}{12} = \dots + \left(\frac{h}{2}\right)\left(-\frac{1}{h} + \gamma\right) + (1)\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) + (1)\left(-\frac{1}{12}\right) - \left(\frac{h}{2}\right)(0.03045h) + \dots \quad (3.44)$$

$$-\frac{13}{12} = \dots - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{12}\right) - 0 + \dots \quad (3.45)$$

$$-\frac{13}{12} = -\frac{13}{12} \quad (3.46)$$

In section 5 I will do more of these and elaborate more, now I want to show one last thing before ending section 3.

In this section I have shown how the Taylor series and binomial expansion extends to the negative side giving hx^{-1} , hx^{-2} and so on, but I noticed something interesting, the value of the hx^{-1} gives the area of that function from $-\infty$ to 0 for example:

the hx^{-1} of e^x is multiplied by 1 and $\int_{-\infty}^0 e^x dx = 1$

the hx^{-1} of 2^x is multiplied by $\frac{1}{\ln 2}$ and $\int_{-\infty}^0 2^x dx = \frac{1}{\ln 2}$

and if the area diverges we will get the regularized area for example:

the hx^{-1} of $(x+1)^1$ is multiplied by $\frac{1}{2}$ and $\int_{-\infty}^0 (x+1)^1 dx = D + \frac{1}{2}$

where D is divergant part and $\frac{1}{2}$ is regularized part,so:

$$r/c \int_{-\infty}^0 hf(x)dx = \frac{f^{-1+h}(0)}{(-1+h)!} \quad (3.47)$$

since the coefficient of hx^{-1} is the constant of integral, ($\int f(x)dx = F(x)$) then I will also get:

$$r/c \int_{-\infty}^0 f(x)dx = \int^0 f(x)dx = F(0) \quad (3.48)$$

In the next section I will explain the regularization of diverging areas more deeply.

4 Regularization of diverging areas

It turns out not only a diverging series has regularization but even diverging areas do so, I will show how to get the values of regularization for $\int_0^1 x^n dx$ for $n < -1$ using 2 different methods

4.1 Method 1

Since $\Gamma(x) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t}t^{x-1}dt$ for $x > 0$ [3] and this domain exists because for $x < 0$ the area diverges which is an issue, but I will ignore this domain and find the area anyways and see what happens

I will split $\int_0^{\infty} e^{-t}t^{x-1}dt$ into $\int_0^1 e^{-t}t^{x-1}dt$ and $\int_1^{\infty} e^{-t}t^{x-1}dt$, the 1 to ∞ part converges for all value of x so the issue is with the 0 to 1 part but there is a simple fix, let us take $\Gamma(0)$:

$$\Gamma(0) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t}t^{-1}dt \quad (4.1)$$

$$\Gamma(0) = \int_0^1 e^{-t}t^{-1}dt + \int_1^{\infty} e^{-t}t^{-1}dt \quad (4.2)$$

Now I will subtract $\frac{1}{t}$ from $\int_0^1 e^{-t}t^{-1}dt$ (since $\frac{1}{t}$ is the first term of the taylor series of $e^{-t}t^{-1}$ and is causing the divergence), doing so will give me $\int_0^1 (e^{-t}t^{-1} - \frac{1}{t})dt$ which converges, Now:

$$\Gamma(0) = \int_0^1 (e^{-t}t^{-1} - \frac{1}{t})dt + \int_1^\infty e^{-t}t^{-1}dt + \int_0^1 \frac{1}{t}dt \quad (4.3)$$

Calculating area numerically and I know $\Gamma(0) = \frac{1}{h} - \gamma$, gives:

$$\frac{1}{h} - \gamma = -0.79659959 + 0.21938393 + \int_0^1 \frac{1}{t}dt \quad (4.4)$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{1}{t}dt = \frac{1}{h} \quad (4.5)$$

Now I will repeat the process for $\Gamma(-1)$:

$$\Gamma(-1) = \int_0^\infty e^{-t}t^{-2}dt \quad (4.6)$$

$$\Gamma(-1) = \int_0^1 e^{-t}t^{-2}dt + \int_1^\infty e^{-t}t^{-2}dt \quad (4.7)$$

Now I will subtract $\frac{1}{t^2}$ and add $\frac{1}{t}$ to $\int_0^1 e^{-t}t^{-2}dt$ (according to the taylor series), doing so will give me $\int_0^1 (e^{-t}t^{-2} - \frac{1}{t^2} + \frac{1}{t})dt$ which converges, Now:

$$\Gamma(-1) = \int_0^1 (e^{-t}t^{-2} - \frac{1}{t^2} + \frac{1}{t})dt + \int_1^\infty e^{-t}t^{-2}dt + r \int_0^1 \frac{1}{t^2}dt - \int_0^1 \frac{1}{t}dt \quad (4.8)$$

Calculating area numerically and since $\Gamma(-1) = -\frac{1}{h} - 1 + \gamma$ and since $\int_0^1 \frac{1}{t}dt = \frac{1}{h}$ from (4.5), gives:

$$-\frac{1}{h} - 1 + \gamma = 0.42871991 + 0.14849551 + r \int_0^1 \frac{1}{t^2}dt - \frac{1}{h} \quad (4.9)$$

$$r \int_0^1 \frac{1}{t^2}dt = -1 \quad (4.10)$$

Repeating this process will give:

$$r \int_0^1 \frac{1}{t^3}dt = -\frac{1}{2} \quad (4.11)$$

$$r \int_0^1 \frac{1}{t^4}dt = -\frac{1}{3} \quad (4.12)$$

$$r \int_0^1 \frac{1}{t^5} dt = -\frac{1}{4} \quad (4.13)$$

so $r/c \int_0^1 x^n dx = \frac{1}{n+1}$, this is obviously true when $n > -1$ but when $n < -1$ it diverges which means I need regularization which means I need to analytically continue the function and since when $n > -1$ I get a perfect $\frac{1}{n+1}$ and since there is only one way to analytically extend a function so the obvious continuation of $\frac{1}{n+1}$ will simply be its other half.

Since the definition of $\Gamma(x)$ is based on integral and this integral diverges when $x < 0$, this means that for $x < 0$ $\Gamma(x)$ is regularized, so $\Gamma(x)$ is a regularized function which makes me wonder if there is another meaning for $\Gamma(x)$ other than the fact that its purpose is to represent the factorial properly.

I can use Method 1 for $\zeta(x)$ which will give me the same results, but what I can conclude from all of this is that if an area or a series diverges with a large value where $\frac{1}{h^n}$ for $n > 1$ the pole will be omitted and there will be a regularization value (normal value), but for $\frac{1}{h^n} + a$ for $n = 1$ (a is normal value constant) there will be no regularization. As if mathematics cares about us where even when a graph diverges this regularization was created so that we can still see, otherwise we would be half blind, since $\frac{1}{h^n} + a$ for $n = 1$ is the last thing that can actually be plotted on a graph before heading to the unknown world.

4.2 Method 2

For method 2 I will have to start by introducing the term "summation equation" for example:

the summation equation of $\sum_{n=1}^x n^0$ is x

the summation equation of $\sum_{n=1}^x n^1$ is $\frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x}{2}$

the summation equation of $\sum_{n=1}^x n^2$ is $\frac{x^3}{3} + \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x}{6}$

the summation equation of $\sum_{n=1}^x \frac{1}{n^s}$ if $s > 0$ is

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^{1+s}}{(-x-n)^s} + \frac{1}{n^s} \right) \quad (4.14)$$

After staring at the summation equations of $\sum_{n=1}^x \frac{1}{n^s}$ for days and using simple pattern recognition I can conclude for any value of b that:

$$\zeta(s) = \int_{-1+b}^{0+b} \left(\sum_{n=1}^x \frac{1}{n^s} \right) dx - \frac{b^{-s+1}}{-s+1} \quad (4.15)$$

This works for complex plane too, hence I used s . Now I will use $s=2$ and $b=0$ so that I have to integrate diverging area:

$$\zeta(2) = \int_{-1}^0 \left(\sum_{n=1}^x \frac{1}{n^2} \right) dx - \frac{0^{-2+1}}{-2+1} \quad (4.16)$$

Using (4.14):

$$\zeta(2) = \int_{-1}^0 \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^{1+2}}{(-x-n)^2} + \frac{1}{n^2} \right) \right) dx - \frac{0^{-2+1}}{-2+1} \quad (4.17)$$

Since the area diverges I will subtract from it $\frac{1}{(x+1)^2}$ which will make it converge now:

$$\zeta(2) = \int_{-1}^0 \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^{1+2}}{(-x-n)^2} + \frac{1}{n^2} \right) + \frac{1}{(x+1)^2} \right) dx - \int_{-1}^0 \frac{1}{(x+1)^2} dx - \frac{0^{-2+1}}{-2+1} \quad (4.18)$$

Calculating the area numerically of $\int_{-1}^0 \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^{1+2}}{(-x-n)^2} + \frac{1}{n^2} \right) + \frac{1}{(x+1)^2} \right) dx$ becomes:

$$\frac{\pi^2}{6} = \frac{\pi^2}{6} - 1 - \int_{-1}^0 \frac{1}{(x+1)^2} dx - \frac{0^{-2+1}}{-2+1} \quad (4.19)$$

$$\int_{-1}^0 \frac{1}{(x+1)^2} dx = -1 - \frac{0^{-2+1}}{-2+1} \quad (4.20)$$

I just realized I could have just integrated $\frac{1}{x^2}$ from 0 to 1 and get same results instead of doing all of this.

So it turns out I could just integrate $\frac{1}{x^n}$ for $n > 1$ from 0 to 1, to get the regularization values since doing so will give me a divergent part (on the right) and normal value part (regularized part on the left):

$$\int_0^1 \frac{1}{(x)^n} dx = \frac{1^{-n+1}}{-n+1} - \frac{0^{-n+1}}{-n+1} \quad (4.21)$$

Using the same idea I can state that:

$$\int_1^{\infty} x^n dx = \frac{\infty^{n+1}}{n+1} - \frac{1^{n+1}}{n+1} \quad (4.22)$$

So the regularization becomes:

$$r/c \int_1^{\infty} x^n dx = -\frac{1}{n+1} \quad (4.23)$$

and since $r/c \int_0^1 x^n dx = \frac{1}{n+1}$ then:

$$r \int_0^{\infty} x^n dx = \frac{1}{n+1} - \frac{1}{n+1} \quad (4.24)$$

Remember $\int_0^1 x^n dx = \frac{1}{n+1}$ gives normal value and regularization is also normal value so we can add them together (they are comparable to each other), which becomes:

$$r \int_0^{\infty} x^n dx = 0 \quad (4.25)$$

Please note this 0 is regularization only not actual area, actual area is divergent (large value not normal value) but now if we remember at the end of section 3 I stated that:

"and if the area diverges we will get the regularized area for example: the hx^{-1} of $(x+1)^1$ is multiplied by $\frac{1}{2}$ and $\int_{-\infty}^0 (x+1)^1 dx = D + \frac{1}{2}$ "

Now I will show that the regularization of $r \int_{-\infty}^0 (x+1)^1 dx = \frac{1}{2}$, since $r \int_0^{\infty} x^n dx = 0$ then $r \int_{-\infty}^0 x^n dx = 0$ so $r \int_{-\infty}^0 (x)^1 dx = 0$ and since $\int_{-\infty}^0 (x+1)^1 dx = \int_{-\infty}^1 (x)^1 dx$ then:

$$r \int_{-\infty}^0 (x)^1 dx + \int_0^1 (x)^1 dx = r \int_{-\infty}^1 (x)^1 dx \quad (4.26)$$

$$0 + \frac{1}{2} = r \int_{-\infty}^1 (x)^1 dx \quad (4.27)$$

since $\int_{-\infty}^0 (x+1)^1 dx = \int_{-\infty}^1 (x)^1 dx$

$$\frac{1}{2} = r \int_{-\infty}^0 (x+1)^1 dx \quad (4.28)$$

Honorable mention:

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{-0.5} \left(\frac{1}{n^s}\right)}{2 - 2^s} \quad (4.29)$$

$$\eta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{-0.5} \frac{(-1)^{1+n}}{n^s} \quad (4.30)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^x \frac{1}{n} = \lim_{m \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{(x+m)!}{x!m!m} - \frac{1}{m} \right) \quad (4.31)$$

$$\ln x = \lim_{p \rightarrow 0} \left(\lim_{m \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{(e^{\frac{1}{p}}x + m)!}{(e^{\frac{1}{p}}x)!m!m} - \frac{1}{m} - \frac{1}{p} - \gamma \right) \right) \quad (4.32)$$

5 Converting area to summation

In this section I will show how to find the convergence/regularisation of summation of $f(n)$ using its mclaurin series multiplying each term of the mclaurin series by its respectable zeta value. I have shown previously how to obtain $-\frac{13}{12}$ the new regularization value by taking into consideration the x^{-1} term of the binomial expansion since it is usually multiplied by a zero and its respectable zeta value is $\zeta(1)$ which is a pole causing the pole and the zero to cancel producing a normal value which is the missing piece that allow us to obtain the correct regularizaion value.

There is two main ways of doing this technique, either we use my new taylor series/binomial extension (from $n=-\infty$ to $n=\infty$) with the zeta function, or use the traditional taylor series/binomial expansion definition (from $n=0$ to $n=\infty$) with the zeta function but with adding the area from 0 to ∞ (since my extension already takes the area into consideration through x^{-1} term).

5.1 Extended defintion method (from $n=-\infty$ to $n=\infty$)

Here I will use the extended deifntion of the taylor series and binomial expansion, first case is working with binomial expansion where $(ax + b)^n$ for $n \geq 0$ when n is an integer for any a and b :

For example $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n+2)^3$, since:

$$r \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n)^3 = 1 + 8 + 27 + 64 + \dots = \frac{1}{120} \quad (5.1)$$

then:

$$r \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n+2)^3 = 27 + 64 + \dots = \frac{1}{120} - 1 - 8 \quad (5.2)$$

then:

$$r \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\dots + 4hn^{-1} + 8n^0 + 12n + 6n^2 + n^3 - \frac{hn^4}{8} + \dots) = -\frac{1079}{120} \quad (5.3)$$

then:

$$r \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\dots + 4hn^{-1}\zeta(1) + 8n^0\zeta(0) + 12n\zeta(-1) + 6n^2\zeta(-2) + n^3\zeta(-3) - \frac{hn^4}{8}\zeta(-4) + \dots) = -\frac{1079}{120} \quad (5.4)$$

then:

$$(\dots + 4h(-\frac{1}{h} + \gamma) - \frac{8}{2} - 1 + 6(-0.03045h + \dots) + (\frac{1}{120} + 0.0054h + \dots) - \frac{h}{8}(0.00799h + \dots) +) = \quad (5.5)$$

I tried my best to add as much h's as possible but space is limited (for example $\zeta(0) = -\frac{1}{2} - \frac{\ln 2\pi}{2}h - 1.003h^2 + \dots$), then:

$$(\dots - 4 - 4 - 1 + 0 + \frac{1}{120} - 0+) = -\frac{1079}{120} \quad (5.6)$$

For $(ax + b)^n$ when n is not positive integer, multiplying the binomial terms by their respective zeta values will not converge since the expansion will have infinite terms with normal values unlike when n is a positive integer (normal value terms will be finite and small value terms will be infinite but it doesnt matter because they are small), and since the growth of $\zeta(-x)$ (when x heads toward ∞) overwhelms the decay of the terms of the binomial expansion this will cause the terms to diverge but they will diverge in an alternating way, just like 1-2+3-4... which converge to $\frac{1}{4}$ so they do probably converge but not in a straightforward way, we will have to find average value which is probably so tough to do.

But since when $(ax + b)^n$ if n is not a positive integer, we will get 2 expansions:

$$\sum_{q=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{n!a^{q+j}b^{n-(q+j)}}{(q+j)!(n-(q+j))!}x^{q+j} \quad (5.7)$$

One is when $j=0$ and the other is when $j=n$, so for example $n=0.5$ for $j=0$ we will have:

$$\left(\dots + \frac{2hx^{-1}}{3} + x^0 + \frac{x^1}{2} - \frac{x^2}{8} + \frac{x^3}{16} - \frac{5x^4}{128} + \dots\right) \quad (5.8)$$

for $j=0.5$ we will have:

$$\left(\dots - \frac{5x^{-3.5}}{128} + \frac{x^{-2.5}}{16} - \frac{x^{-1.5}}{8} + \frac{x^{-0.5}}{2} + x^{0.5} - \frac{2hx^{1.5}}{3} + \dots\right) \quad (5.9)$$

Now I will find the value of regularization, since $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty}(n)^{0.5} = \zeta(-0.5) = -0.207886$ then $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty}(n+1)^{0.5} = -1.207886$, so we should get -1.207886 :

$$\left(\dots + \frac{4h\zeta(2)}{15} + \frac{2h\zeta(1)}{3} + \zeta(0) + \frac{\zeta(-1)}{2} - \frac{\zeta(-2)}{8} + \frac{\zeta(-3)}{16} - \frac{5\zeta(-4)}{128} + \dots\right) \quad (5.10)$$

then:

$$\left(\dots 0 - \frac{2}{3} - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{24} + 0 + \frac{1}{1920} + 0 - \frac{7}{64512} + \dots\right) \quad (5.11)$$

I will sum the terms from the 0 all the way to right:

$$0, -0.6667, -1.1667, -1.2083, -1.2078, -1.2079 \quad (5.12)$$

As we can see it does seem to approach -1.207886 but if we keep on adding more terms we will eventually diverge in an alternating way, since if we fast forward we will get $(0.002291)(-54827)$ which is approximately 257 the term after will be even bigger but negative and so on.

If I use the other expansion when $j=0.5$ it will converge (since I will be using $\zeta(1.5), \zeta(2.5), \zeta(3.5), \zeta(4.5)\dots$ which converges to 1 and since the binomial also converges to 0 so the multiplied sum will converge) and it will approach -1.207886 but I only checked for few digits because convergence is slow (I am not sure if it will be spot on though), but if I use $b > 1$ the $j=0.5$ expansion will diverge too so it will not work for all cases.

But nevertheless I find it to be interesting that even though the series eventually diverges at the start it does seem to approach the value I am expecting. Anyways, for binomial expansion we have (if n is a positive integer it will be exact, if not then it will approach the regularisation/convergence slightly then might diverge):

$$r/c \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (ak + b)^n = \sum_{q=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{n! a^{q+j} b^{n-(q+j)}}{(q+j)!(n-(q+j))!} \zeta(-(q+j)) \quad (5.13)$$

Now I will explain what will happen when this technique is used for mclaurin series of common functions. The first thing we can notice is that since mclaurin series is divided by $q!$ and will get multiplied by $\zeta(q)$ which is related to factorial so the growth of $\zeta(q)$ will be comparable to the decay of the terms of the mclaurin series.

I will use $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^v (\cos(\pi x)) \approx \sum_{q=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(\frac{\pi(q-v)}{2})}{(q-v)!} \zeta(-q)$ as an example and show where the issues start to immerge for diffrent values of v , If v is a positive integer there will be no issues, If v is a negative odd integer there will be extra pole in the results (I suspect that this pole will get cancelled if I take into consideration the divergant parts not only the regularized part), If v is a negative even integer I will have to flip the sign of hx^{-1} component in order for things to work. If v is not an integer then things will not work, luckily I was able to find a robust work around that will work for all value of v and for binomial expansion too and basically most functions, I will show the method in next subsection.

But the main idea in the work around method I will have to add area from 0 to ∞ and this is why when using the extended method when v is a negative even integer I have to flip sign, since when v is even, the function will be symmetrical so the area from $-\infty$ to 0 will have same sign of 0 to ∞ but $\zeta(1)$ will flip the sign since it is $(-\frac{1}{0})$, which mean if the function is odd and it converges on one side and diverges on the other, the area/summation of the convergent side will be equal and opposite to the regularisation of the divergent side, if it diverges on both sides then the regularisation of the area/summation will be opposite in sign, for example $r \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} p^n = -\sum_{n=-\infty}^0 p^n$ for $p > 0$ (I do not know how complex plane behaves)

But this means If I sum from -1 to $-\infty$ I will not face an issue with area being different, since if I sum from -1 to $-\infty$ I will use the area from $-\infty$ to 0,

which I already have in the x^{-1} component of the mclauring series/ binomial expansion (also I have to flip the signs of the $\zeta(n)$ for odd n), which makes me wonder what causes this bias, why is the math forcing me to sum from -1 to $-\infty$?

5.2 Traditional defintion method (from $n=0$ to $n=\infty$)

This method is very simple, I use the traditional binomial or mclaurin expansion and multiply each component by its respective zeta value (doing this will give me the "convertor" value) and then add the integral from 0 to ∞ (since my extension already takes the integral into consideration through x^{-1} component so I will have to compensate). So:

$$r/c \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f(n) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^n(0)}{(n)!} \zeta(-n) + r/c \int_0^{\infty} f(x) dx \quad (5.14)$$

Now I will show how I got $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(e^n-1)} \approx \frac{\pi^2}{6} - \frac{\ln 2\pi}{2} - \frac{1}{24}$, since mclaurin series:

$$\frac{1}{n(e^n - 1)} = \sum_{k=-2}^{\infty} (-1)^{(1+k)} \frac{\zeta(-(k+1))n^k}{\Gamma(k+2)} \quad (5.15)$$

then:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^n(0)}{(n)!} \zeta(-n) = \sum_{k=-2}^{\infty} (-1)^{(1+k)} \frac{\zeta(-(k+1))}{\Gamma(k+2)} \zeta(-k) \quad (5.16)$$

so:

$$\sum_{k=-2}^{\infty} (-1)^{(1+k)} \frac{\zeta(-(k+1))}{\Gamma(k+2)} \zeta(-k) = \frac{1}{2h} - \frac{\gamma}{2} + \frac{\pi^2}{6} - \frac{1}{24} \quad (5.17)$$

Now I have to add $r/c \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{x(e^x-1)} dx$ but since the integral diverges then I have to take its regularization. There is multiple of ways to obtain the value of the integral. I can find it numerically just like how I did in section 4.1 or use the definition [4]:

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{s-1}}{(e^x - 1)} dx \quad (5.18)$$

so:

$$\zeta(0) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(0)} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{-1}}{(e^x - 1)} dx \quad (5.19)$$

so:

$$\zeta(0)\Gamma(0) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{-1}}{(e^x - 1)} dx \quad (5.20)$$

then:

$$\left(-\frac{1}{2} - \frac{\ln 2\pi}{2}h - 1.003h^2 \dots\right) \left(\frac{1}{h} - \gamma + 0.989h^2 + \dots\right) = r \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{-1}}{(e^x - 1)} dx \quad (5.21)$$

then:

$$\left(-\frac{1}{2h} - \frac{\ln 2\pi}{2} + \frac{\gamma}{2} - 0.47257h + \dots\right) = r \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{-1}}{(e^x - 1)} dx \quad (5.22)$$

-0.47257h is a first degree zero so negligible, so:

$$\left(-\frac{1}{2h} - \frac{\ln 2\pi}{2} + \frac{\gamma}{2}\right) = r \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{-1}}{(e^x - 1)} dx \quad (5.23)$$

then:

$$\sum_{k=-2}^{\infty} (-1)^{(1+k)} \frac{\zeta(-(k+1))}{\Gamma(k+2)} \zeta(-k) + r \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{-1}}{(e^x - 1)} dx = \left(\frac{1}{2h} - \frac{\gamma}{2} + \frac{\pi^2}{6} - \frac{1}{24}\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2h} - \frac{\ln 2\pi}{2} + \frac{\gamma}{2}\right) \quad (5.24)$$

so:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(e^n - 1)} \approx \frac{\pi^2}{6} - \frac{\ln 2\pi}{2} - \frac{1}{24} \quad (5.25)$$

Doing this will also give:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{n}{(e^n - 1)} \approx \frac{\pi^2}{6} - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{24} \quad (5.26)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{n^3}{(e^n - 1)} \approx \frac{6\pi^4}{90} - \frac{1}{240} \quad (5.27)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{n^5}{(e^n - 1)} \approx \frac{120\pi^6}{945} + \frac{1}{504} \quad (5.28)$$

The reason here it is an approximation and not perfect values is because here the mclaurin series has $\frac{\zeta(-(n+1))}{n!}$ which causes the value to decay slowly since $n!$ decay is barely stronger than the growth of the $\zeta(-n)$ but the values are multiplied by another $\zeta(n)$ so they will eventually diverge (even though in the above situations the rest of the terms are 0 but if we take limit the divergence will be in term of a pole so cancelling each other and give the values that make it imperfect) , but nevertheless, the accuracy is good ranging from 13 to 16 digits and do not forget that the common functions we use usually have $n!$ in the denominator which will be multiplied by one zeta only so the terms will decay without making a comeback. For example, when trying to find e^{-x^2} there will be 4 digit accuracy for e^{-x^3} it will be even worse, because the mclauring series of e^{-x^2} has $\frac{1}{2!}$ which has half the decay, so the zeta function will catch up faster, e^{-x^3} has $\frac{1}{3!}$ which is even worse.

I can use equation (5.14) to find the regularization of diverging integrals, for example:

$$r \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2^n}{2} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\ln 2)^k}{2(k!)} \zeta(-k) + r \int_0^{\infty} \frac{2^x}{2} dx \quad (5.29)$$

becomes

$$-1 = -0.27865247956 + r \int_0^{\infty} \frac{2^x}{2} dx \quad (5.30)$$

so:

$$-0.72134752044 = r \int_0^{\infty} \frac{2^x}{2} dx \quad (5.31)$$

so:

$$-1.44269504088 = -\frac{1}{\ln 2} = r \int_0^{\infty} 2^x dx \quad (5.32)$$

also:

$$\int_0^{\infty} 2^x dx = \frac{2^{\infty}}{\ln 2} - \frac{2^0}{\ln 2} = \frac{2^{\infty}}{\ln 2} - \frac{1}{\ln 2} \quad (5.33)$$

so regularization of 2^{∞} is 0 ($r2^{\infty} = 0$), In here the convertor value is perfect since it involved multiplying $\frac{(\ln 2)^k}{2(k!)}$ by $\zeta(-k)$ and since $\zeta(k) =$

$2^k \pi^{k-1} \sin(\frac{\pi x}{2}) \Gamma(1-k) \zeta(1-k)$ [4], then $\zeta(-k) = \frac{\zeta(k+1)}{2(2^k) \pi^k \sin(\frac{\pi(k+1)}{2}) \Gamma(-k)}$ and since the *sin* (sin causes multiplication by 2) and ζ will have no effect on divergence and since $\frac{1}{\Gamma(-k)}$ has same growth as $\frac{k!}{\pi}$, so we will end up with $\zeta(-k) = \frac{k!}{(2^k) \pi (\pi^k)}$, now if we multiply this by $\frac{(\ln 2)^k}{2(k!)}$ we will get $\frac{(\ln 2)^k}{2(2^k) \pi (\pi^k)}$ which converges.

$$\mathbf{6} \quad \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(x)} dx = e$$

Now I will show that $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(x)} dx = e$, in my early math days when working with binomial expansion where I used to plot the binomial expansion graphically I noticed for example the expansion of $(x+1)^{0.5}$ I could use $j=0$ and $j=0.5$ (j is from equation (5.7)), which made me wonder what will happen if I take $j=0.1$ or $j=0.05$ or any other j value, if we take those value and plot the resulting expansion, the graph will diverge but in an alternating fasion, and I know that when we diverge in an alternating way (flipping signs) we might converge, so I believed we can take any configuration (any value for j), but if all values of j will give correct expansion, then I can take the average which is simply the integral of the function that represents the series of binomial expansion from $-\infty$ to ∞ , so:

$$(ax+b)^n = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{n! a^t b^{n-t}}{t!(n-t)!} x^t dt \quad (6.1)$$

For mclaurin series we will have:

$$f(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{f^t(0)}{t!} x^t dt \quad (6.2)$$

So if $f(x) = e^x$ then:

$$e^x = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{t!} x^t dt \quad (6.3)$$

if $x=1$ then:

$$e^1 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x!} 1^x dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(x+1)} dx \quad (6.4)$$

since I am integrating from $-\infty$ to ∞ then shifting a function will not change the answer so:

$$e = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(x)} dx \quad (6.5)$$

Now till this point everything I have shown in this section is based on assumptions that could be so wrong, but:

if:

$$e = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(-x)} dx \quad (6.6)$$

and it is trivial that (since it converges normally):

$$\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{1}{\Gamma(-x)} dx = 2.807770242 \quad (6.7)$$

then:

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(-x)} dx = e - 2.807770242 = -0.089488413541 \quad (6.8)$$

Now I will use equation (5.14):

$$r/c \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f(n) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^n(0)}{(n)!} \zeta(-n) + r/c \int_0^{\infty} f(x) dx \quad (6.9)$$

$f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(-x)}$:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(-n)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^n(0)}{(n)!} \zeta(-n) + \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(-x)} dx \quad (6.10)$$

since my prediction says $\int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(-x)} dx = -0.089488413541$ and it is trivial that $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(-n)} = 0$, so:

$$0 = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^n(0)}{(n)!} \zeta(-n) - 0.089488413541 \quad (6.11)$$

so:

$$0.089488413541 = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^n(0)}{(n)!} \zeta(-n) \quad (6.12)$$

In order to find the convertor value manually, I need the mclaurin series of $\frac{1}{\Gamma(-x)}$ then multiply each component of the mclaurin series by its respective zeta value, so mclaurin series is:

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(-x)} = -x + \gamma x^2 + 0.655878x^3 - 0.042x^4 - 0.16654x^5 - 0.0422x^6 + 0.0096x^7 + \dots \quad (6.13)$$

Now multiply by zeta values:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^n(0)}{(n)!} \zeta(-n) = -\zeta(-1) + \gamma \zeta(-2) + 0.65588 \zeta(-3) - 0.042 \zeta(-4) - 0.16654 \zeta(-5) - 0.0422 \zeta(-6) + \dots \quad (6.14)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^n(0)}{(n)!} \zeta(-n) = 0.0895 \quad (6.15)$$

As we can see the value I got (0.0895) is so close to the prediction (0.089488413541), if i use more terms for the mclaurin series I will get more accurate result, nevertheless, this confirms that $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(x)} dx = e$, even though the integral diverges, but it diverges in an alternating way, so it converges. But this also shows that equations (6.1) and (6.2) are true.

If we plot $\int_0^x \frac{1}{\Gamma(t)} dt$ visually it will look a bit odd (also it will converge to 2.80777 instead of e), and that is because integrating from 0 to x deletes the constant, so we have to add it manually (using equation (3.48)), which is -0.089488413541, now if we plot $\int_0^x \frac{1}{\Gamma(t)} dt - 0.089488413541$, visually it will look perfect and that is because the integral of every function has 1 perfect integral with a specific height/constant (intersection with y-axis), so:

$$\int f(x) dx = \int^x f(t) dt = \int_0^x f(t) dt + r/c \int_{-\infty}^0 f(t) dt \quad (6.16)$$

Now I will show the integral from 0 to ∞ of more functions:

$$\int_0^{\infty} \cos(x) dx = 0 \quad (6.17)$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \sin(x) dx = 1 \quad (6.18)$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \cos(\pi x) dx = 0 \quad (6.19)$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \sin(\pi x) dx = \frac{1}{\pi} \quad (6.20)$$

In order to get these values, we can use summation/area convertor method (equation 5.14), or check the value of x^{-1} component of the mclaurin series (equation 3.47) then flip sign for \sin , or we could add the areas manually, for example, for $\int_0^{\infty} \sin(x) dx$, from 0 to π the area is 2 then from π to 2π the area is -2, and its a repeating cycle so:

$$2 - 2 + 2 - 2 + 2 - 2 + \dots = 2(1 - 1 + 1 - 1 + 1 - 1 + \dots) = 2(\eta(0)) = 1 \quad (6.21)$$

At the start of this section I have shown we can take any value of j, so for any value of j:

$$(ax + b)^n = \sum_{q=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{n! a^{q+j} b^{n-(q+j)}}{(q+j)!(n-(q+j))!} x^{q+j} \quad (6.22)$$

For taylor series, for any value of j:

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{f^{n+j}(a)}{(n+j)!} (x-a)^{n+j} \quad (6.23)$$

Which also means that for any value of j:

$$\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n+j)!} = e \quad (6.24)$$

7 Differentiating and integrating polynomials

In section 3 I have worked with different types of functions (integrating and differentiating them) but they are all based on functions that can be expressed as a mclaurin series or binomial expansion which allows me to shift naturally so that I can express these functions in terms of $\dots x^{-1+h}, x^h, x^{1+h}, x^{2+h} \dots etc$ instead of $\dots x^{-1}, x^0, x^1, x^2 \dots$, even though in previous section I have shown how I believe we can pick any configuration $\dots x^{-1+j}, x^j, x^{1+j}, x^{2+j} \dots etc$ even

though they will not converge normally, but using h which is an infinitely small component will still converge normally due to its negligible effect. But working with polynomials is a bit different, since they are not based on an infinite series, so in order for me to differentiate them and integrate them without losing information I will have to simply multiply them by x^h (in Taylor series and binomial expansion I have to shift not only multiply for perfect results), for example, $x + x^0$ becomes $x^{1+h} + x^h$, now if I differentiate this, I will get hx^{-1+h} which will synchronize perfectly with etc: e^x when I expand it with shifted h .

8 Summary

1. $(x + 1)^1 \neq x + 1$, $(x + 1)^0 \neq (x + 2)^0$, due to hidden zeroes
2. $x^0 \neq 1$, $3^0 > 2^0 > 1^0$ since the rate at which the 1 is approached matters.
3. $\int \frac{1}{x} dx = \frac{x^0}{0}$, using $\ln x$ is only good enough when finding definite integral but for indefinite integral we have to be perfect so we have to use $\frac{x^0}{0}$ but using $\frac{x^0}{0}$ involves dividing by zero which is an issue. So we have to integrate x^{-1+h} instead.
4. Differentiating different constants gives different results, assuming it is a default zero loses information.
5. Each function has its constant of integral embedded inside of it, and we can find this information at the x^{-1} term of the Maclaurin series.
6. The constant of integral is also the regularised/converging area of the function we are integrating from $-\infty$ to 0
7. In the traditional sense all zeroes are the same, but doing so loses valuable information, since the rate at which we approach the zero matters (the same can be said about poles). So we have to work just a little on the right of the zero, which causes clear differentiation between different types of zeroes, preserving information. (the magnitude and the direction of the first degree zero depends on the magnitude and the direction of the first derivative at that point)
8. Differentiating x^0 and integrating x^{-1} is faulty, use x^h and x^{-1+h} instead. and doing this forces us to use x^{1+h} , x^{2+h} , x^{-2+h} , x^{-3+h} , etc

9. Not all poles are the same, the rate at which we approach the pole matters. If the right side of the pole is a large positive value then the pole is positive, if it is a large negative value then the pole is negative. ($\frac{1}{x}$ is a positive pole since $\frac{1}{h}$ is positive)

10. All Taylor series extend to the negative side and all binomial expansions extend to the negative side and positive side (due to the zeroes).

11. Regularisation is when a value, integral or a sum diverges, and the divergent part is omitted taking only the normal value (first degree pole being the only special case that does not get omitted).

12. Why does the x^{-1} term of the Maclaurin/binomial expansion give area from $-\infty$ to 0 rather than 0 to ∞ ? which forces me to sum $f(n)$ from $n=-1$ to $n=-\infty$ when using Extended definition method (section 5.1).

13. $\int_0^\infty f(x)dx$ and $\sum_{n=1}^\infty f(n)$ are interchangeable by adding a value I call the convertor which can be obtained by multiplying the terms of the Maclaurin series of $f(x)$ by their respective zeta values.

14. Any Taylor series and binomial expansion can be written in infinite different ways.

15. If we diverge in alternating fashion we might still converge, just like how $1-2+3-4+5\dots$ gives $\frac{1}{4}$ and $\int_{-\infty}^\infty \frac{1}{\Gamma(x)}dx = e$

9 References

[1] M. Khalkhali, "Why $\infty! = \sqrt{2\pi}$," Pizza Seminar Talk, Department of Mathematics, University of Western Ontario, April 1, 2015. Slides available at <https://www.math.uwo.ca/faculty/khalkhali/files/Pizza2015.pdf>.

[2] T. Tao, "The Euler-Maclaurin formula, Bernoulli numbers, the zeta function, and real-variable analytic continuation," blog post, April 10, 2010. Available at: <https://terrytao.wordpress.com/2010/04/10/the-euler-maclaurin-formula/>

[3] Weisstein, Eric W. "Gamma Function." From *MathWorld* – A Wolfram Resource. Available at <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/GammaFunction.html>.

[4] E. W. Weisstein, "Riemann Zeta Function," From *MathWorld* – A Wolfram Resource. Available at: <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/RiemannZetaFunction.html>.

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